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CONTENTS

ARTICLES

- Vasile Zotic, Oana-Ramona Ilovan, Claudia-Florentina Dobre**
The Traumas of Bărăgan and Siberia: Identity, Place
Attachment and Resilience in the Deportees' Life Stories..... 9
- Ketevan Svanidze, Shorena Bolkvadze**
Woman and Postcolonial Trauma..... 26
- Tamila Davitadze, Nana Mazmishvili**
Religion and Women in Adjara..... 39
- Georgeta Nazarska**
Muslim Women under the 'Care' of the State
Women's Organizations in Bulgaria (1950s–1980s).....52
- Yelis Erolova**
The Spontaneous and Forced Assimilation of the Turkish Women in
Urban and Rural Environment during the Socialist Period in
Bulgaria (Examples from the Svishtov Region)..... 65
- Salih Borovin**
Memories in the Present: The Post-Memory of Assimilationist
Policies Toward Muslims in Bulgaria (1960s–1970s)..... 86
- Mariyana Piskova**
Muslims in the 'lens' of photo propaganda,
1950s - 1980s in the 20th Century..... 97
- Jumber Vardmanidze**
Conformity and Consensus in Southwestern Georgia after the
establishment of Russian Imperial authority: the role of the Russian
Empire in the resettlement of the local population (Muhajirism).....124
- Nana Kajaia, Asmat Ardzenadze**
Muslim Women of Ajara: Certain Aspects of Their
Sociocultural and Sociolinguistic Portrait..... 138
- Svitlana Kryvoruchko**
Reflections on the Archetype of Home in
the Feature Film "Homeward".....150

Sercan Eklemezler, Selda Adilođlu From Minority to Immigrant: The Education and Cross-Country Teaching Experiences of Turks of Bulgaria.....	169
Maria Mateoniu Micu The relationship between orthodoxy and politics in dictatorship and democracy The exemplary case of Saint Nicholas Monastery (Romania).....	186
Cem Yılmaz Budan Künstlerroman in Turkish Literature and an Original Work of The Genre: Nahid Sırrı's Novel "Yıldız Olmak Kolay Mı?".....	207
Maya Angelova Outsiders and Runaways around 1965: Approaches to the Problem in the Context of Bulgarian Literature and Culture.....	228
Antony Hoyte-West Languages, Language Choice, and Multilingualism in Pajtim Statovci's Novel Bolla.....	252
Neda-Maria Panayotova Freedom and Identity in Guy Gavriel Kay's Novel Tigana.....	265
Bekim Sele, Durim Kryziu Documentary Films Produced by Kosovafilm (1975–2003).....	272
İlhan Aslan Byzantine-Pecheneg Conflicts in the Balkans.....	287
Eka Vardoshvili Faces of Women Victims of Inequality in the Prose of Alexander Kazbegi.....	306
Vladimir Janev, Dragan Zajkovski The "New Wave" in Yugoslav rock and roll in the 1980s (Musical Creation within Totalitarian Frameworks).....	314
BOOK REVIEW	
Claudia-Florentina Dobre The environment between struggles and heritage.....	322
Mihail Gruev An Objective and Critical Look at Mustafa Kemal and his Era.....	329

СЪДЪРЖАНИЕ

СТАТИИ

- Vasile Zotic, Oana-Ramona Povan, Claudia-Florentina Dobre**
The Traumas of Bărăgan and Siberia: Identity, Place
Attachment and Resilience in the Deportees' Life Stories..... 9
- Ketevan Svanidze, Shorena Bolkvadze**
Woman and Postcolonial Trauma.....26
- Tamila Davitadze, Nana Mazmishvili**
Religion and Women in Adjara..... 39
- Georgeta Nazarska**
Muslim Women under the 'Care' of the State
Women's Organizations in Bulgaria (1950s–1980s).....52
- Йелис Еролова**
Естествена и насилствена асимилация на турските жени в
градска и селска среда през социалистическия период в
България (примери от района на Свищов)..... 65
- Салих Боровин**
Спомени в настоящето: „постпаметта“ за асимилационните
политики към мюсюлманите в България (1960–1970-те години)..... 86
- Марияна Пискова**
Мюсюлманите в „обектива“ на
фотопропагандата 50-те – 80-те г. на XX век.....97
- Jumber Vardmanidze**
Conformity and Consensus in Southwestern Georgia after the
establishment of Russian Imperial authority: the role of the Russian
Empire in the resettlement of the local population (Muhajirism).....124
- Nana Kajaia, Asmat Ardzenadze**
Muslim Women of Ajara: Certain Aspects of Their.....138
- Svitlana Kryvoruchko**
Reflections on the Archetype of Home in
the Feature Film “Homeward”.....150

Sercan Eklemezler, Selda Adiloğlu From Minority to Immigrant: The Education and Cross-Country Teaching Experiences of Turks of Bulgaria.....	169
Maria Mateoniu Micu The relationship between orthodoxy and politics in dictatorship and democracy The exemplary case of Saint Nicholas Monastery (Romania).....	186
Cem Yılmaz Budan Künstlerroman in Turkish Literature and an Original Work of The Genre: Nahid Sırrı's Novel "Yıldız Olmak Kolay Mı?".....	207
Мая Ангелова Аутсайдери и и бегълци около 1965 година: подстъпи към проблема с оглед на българската литература и култура.....	228
Antony Hoyte-West Languages, Language Choice, and Multilingualism in Pajtim Statovci's Novel Bolla.....	252
Neda-Maria Panayotova Freedom and Identity in Guy Gavriel Kay's Novel Tigana.....	265
Bekim Sele, Durim Kryziu Documentary Films Produced by Kosovafilm (1975–2003).....	272
İlhan Aslan Byzantine-Pecheneg Conflicts in the Balkans.....	287
Eka Vardoshvili Faces of Women Victims of Inequality in the Prose of Alexander Kazbegi.....	306
Vladimir Janev, Dragan Zajkovski The "New Wave" in Yugoslav rock and roll in the 1980s (Musical Creation within Totalitarian Frameworks).....	314
РЕЦЕНЗИИ	
Claudia-Florentina Dobre The environment between struggles and heritage.....	322
Михаил Груев Обективен и критичен поглед към Мустафа Кемал и неговата епоха.....	329